

TURIZM VA MEHMONXONALARDA UMUMIY OVQATLANISH XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

Aliyeva Musaffo G'ayrat qizi

Davlat texnika universiteti doktoranti
musaffo1414@gmail.com +998907220014
ORCID 0000-0003-1886-2920

Nafasova Zuhra Alijon qizi

Qarshi Davlat texnika universiteti talabasi
E-mail: nafasovazuhra0@gmail.com +998919561224
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15496837>

Annotation. This article is dedicated to econometric models for the development of catering services in tourism and hotels. The development of the tourism sector directly affects catering services in hotels. Econometric models are used to improve the efficiency of these services and predict future trends. The following key variables are considered when creating econometric models: tourist flow, hotel occupancy, catering service revenue, price level, service quality index, consumer expenditures, and regional gross domestic product.

Keywords:

Tourism, hotel, econometric model, tourism sector, catering, future trends, forecasting, tourist flow, hotel occupancy, catering service revenue, price level, service quality index, consumer expenditures, regional gross domestic product.

Introduction Tourism, one of the service sectors for the development of new Uzbekistan, plays a major role in the development of countries. Tourism is a temporary travel of people outside their permanent residence and a stay there for a certain period of time, that is, to explore places, enjoy culture and nature. Tourism is one of the important sectors of the economy, which contributes to the economic development of countries, namely, the creation of jobs and the strengthening of international relations. There are several types of tourism. They:

- ecological tourism
- cultural tourism
- beach tourism
- extreme tourism
- medical tourism
- business tourism.

Tourism is of great importance for countries. For example, it brings significant income to the country's economy, promotes cultural exchange,

creates new jobs, and develops the infrastructure of the regions. Uzbekistan has great potential in the tourism sector, attracting tourists with historical cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, the Chimyan Mountains, the Aral Sea, and other attractions. In addition, the tourism industry is one of the leading sectors of the world economy and is a promising sector that brings high income to the national economy. The tourism sector is also developing well in our country. Uzbekistan has more than 7,300 cultural heritage sites, such as historical monuments, monuments built with the high talent of our great ancestors, and sacred places, and most of them are included in the UNESCO list. Therefore, in recent years, our state has been adopting many regulatory and legal documents to develop this area. In particular, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2021 No. PF-6199 "On measures to further improve the state management system in the fields of tourism, sports and cultural heritage," the Cultural Heritage Agency was established under the Ministry of Tourism and Sports.

Given that the main tasks of the agency include the identification, registration, protection, promotion of tangible cultural heritage objects, maintaining a state register, electronic catalog, state cadastre, determining protected boundaries, and exercising state control in the field, it is important to conduct systematic scientific and methodological research on the further development of historical and cultural tourism in our country. Thus, it is relevant to analyze the current state of historical and cultural tourism, its development prospects, and its impact on the national economy. First of all, it is necessary to determine the content of the concept of "historical and cultural tourism". For example, efforts are being made to develop historical and cultural tourism in the Kashkadarya region. In particular, for the development of tourism, the number of places to rest should be further increased, and hotels should meet the demand. There are also many interesting historical monuments in the Kashkadarya region that attract tourists. For example, there are historical monuments that have stood the test of time, such as Oqsaroy, Kokgumbaz, and Amir Temur Cave. No matter how much we talk about the attractions in Kashkadarya, we will never reach the end.

In the scientific works of foreign scientists who conducted scientific research on econometric modeling of the development of hotel and catering services in the context of innovative development trends and increasing sustainability of tourism, they cite 5 main components of the priority factors of the development of the industry today. In particular, the implementation of the

optimal spatial distribution of hotel and catering facilities in the region, the establishment of innovative technical and technological measures in the development of hotel and catering services in the region, the development of optimal options for organizing hotel and catering services that ensure production efficiency in the region, decision-making at the level of the strategy for the prospective development of tourism and catering services, and the improvement of the management system in hotel and catering services are listed as important tasks.

In modern conditions, the process of forming a mechanism for determining the factors of development of catering services in hotels in tourism and hotels is accompanied by a full-fledged scientific research process. Here, the formulation of the problem gives rise to specific goals and objectives. Implementation methods are formed in accordance with the nature of the tasks. In the future, based on the results, important factors are assessed for significance. Below we will dwell on the classification of modern approaches to the influence factors considered in studies of econometric modeling of the development of tourism and catering services.

Global Market Entry: The country's development of eco-tourism is recognized through the popularization of green tourism.

Ecological certifications and labels: Tourism services developed on the basis of a green economy can have ecological certifications. This shows that the brand is environmentally responsible.

There are several ways to contribute to sustainable development in the formation of a national tourism brand:

The main development of this direction is the development of national dishes and traditional culinary culture in hotels, the creation of an exclusive menu of national dishes for tourists, the organization of master classes in cooking, the improvement of the skills of chefs and waiters, prompt service, the analysis of customer feedback, the introduction of electronic menus and online ordering systems, the organization of special discounts and promotions for hotel restaurants, and active advertising on social networks. By implementing these directions, it is necessary to further develop catering services in the tourism sector, become competitive in the international arena, and create an unforgettable gastronomic experience for guests. Additional measures such as studying foreign experience and adapting advanced restaurant systems to the local market, collaborating with the world's leading chefs and inviting them to conduct master classes, introducing a certification system for hotels and

restaurants in accordance with international standards, promoting dishes specific to each region, training employees based on international hospitality standards, offering an individual approach and personalized services in hotels, creating a room delivery service in hotel restaurants, developing a fast delivery system in tourist areas, holding discounts and promotions to attract customers during seasons, and expanding the services of hotel restaurants for large events will help develop the catering system in hotels, increase the number of tourists, and provide high-quality service to customers. In addition, creating special restaurant corners decorated with handicraft products, i.e. increasing the number of interiors decorated in the national style, organizing themed evenings with live music, folklore performances or theatrical performances, live demonstrations of the traditional cooking process for tourists, adapting the interior design of restaurants and cafes to the tourist brand, organizing green areas, outdoor dining areas, establishing continuous training programs for specialists working in the hotel and restaurant sector, and establishing bonus and incentive systems to increase employee motivation will also help further develop this area. Now, let's talk about tourism, first of all, tourism plays a major role in the development of countries. Tourism is a temporary trip of people outside of their permanent tourism and staying there for a certain period of time to relax, that is, to discover places, enjoy culture and nature.

In conclusion, to develop catering in tourism and hotels, it would be appropriate not only to provide food, but also to create an unforgettable gastronomic experience for tourists, promote national dishes and improve the quality of service, and also to make friends with our rich history, as well as our national costumes, dishes and national values. Then we can see a clear increase in the development indicator in the tourism sector. Thus, in conclusion, the development of the catering sector increases the attractiveness of tourism and directly affects the profitability of the hotel business.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining, Turizm, sport va madaniy meros sohasidagi davlat boshqaruvi tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora tadbirlari to'g'risidagi" gi PF-6199-farmoni.2021-yil 6-aprel.//www.lex.uz
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining, Buxoro, Samarqand, Xiva va Shahrisabz shaharlarida xavfsiz turizmni ta'minlash chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida" gi 939-son qarori.23.11.2017-yil.
3. Дмитриевский. Ю.Д.Туристские районы мира.Смоленск, 2000.224с.

4. M.G'.Aliyeva "Эконометрический анализ влияния туристического потока на развитие услуг общественного питания в гостиничном секторе Узбекистана" *Yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot* 2025-yil, fevral. № 2-son.
- 5 Aliyeva, M. (2023). Formation of management system of scientific and technological development of industrial enterprisesforeign experiences and possibilities of their application in uzbekistan. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11 Part 2), 14–20.
6. Aliyeva, Musaffo. "Economic management mechanism of innovation processes in industrial enterprises." *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology* 3 (2023): 287-290.
7. Yuldashev, S., & Aliyeva, M. (2024). Application of agile management method in the management of modern enterprises. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 3(30), 139–142.
8. Makhmanazarovna, R. M. (2021). The importance of a synergy approach to teaching an econometrics in the direction of the economy. In *international conference on multidisciplinary research and innovative technologies* (Vol. 2, pp. 5-7).
9. Karimova, S. (2024). Elektron tijorat platformalarini takomillashtirishda virtual ekotizimlarning o' rni. *Raqamli iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari*, 4(4), 26-33.
10. www.stat.uz–O'zbekiston Respublikasi Davlat statistika qo'mitasi.
11. Международный туризм сократился в 2020-году до уровня 1990-год.<http://iqtisodiyot.tsue.uz/>
12. Равшанова, М. М. (2024). Значение педагогических экспериментов в развитии эконометрических навыков учащихся. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1 (118)), 836-839.
13. Karimova, S. (2023). Elektron tijorat infratuzilmasini rivojlantirish asosida samaradorlikni oshirish yo'llari. *Raqamli iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari*, 3(4), 46-55.
14. Рахимов, А. (2022). Aholiga turizm va umumiy ovqatlanish xizmatlari rivojida ichki va yondosh tarmoqlarning ta'sirini baholash (Qashqadaryo viloyati misolida). *Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim*, 23(4), 397-402.

